

The Preparation of Methyl and Ethyl Iodides from the Corresponding Toluene Sulphonates

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The preparation of methyl iodide from dimethyl sulphate is a well established method but suffers from the disadvantage that only one methyl group is converted to methyl iodide. It has been found that the dimethyl sulphate can be replaced by methyl toluene sulphonate with satisfactory results. Ethyl iodide can be prepared by a similar method.

EXPERIMENTAL

(1) *Methyl Iodide*.—42 gms. of potassium iodide were dissolved in 42 c.c. of water and 47 grams of methyl-*p*-toluene sulphonate added. The mixture was distilled from a sand-bath. The yield of dry, redistilled methyl iodide was 30 grams or 84.5%.

(2) *Ethyl Iodide*.—42 gms. of potassium iodide were dissolved in 42 c.c. of water and boiled on a sand-bath under a reflux condenser. During the course of two hours 50 grams of ethyl-*p*-toluene sulphonate were added; when the addition was complete the mixture was heated for a further half hour. The ethyl iodide was then distilled from a water-bath. The yield of dry, redistilled product was 26 grams or 66.6% of theory. When the ethyl toluene sulphonate was added all at once and the reaction completed by boiling for 2½ hours, the yield was 25 grams. The gradual addition of the ethyl toluene sulphonate effects very little improvement in the yield.

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